

PRINCIPLES AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ISRAEL'S POLICY TOWARD THE EU

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***Abstract:** Relationships with the EU are a strategic asset and a major component of the State of Israel. Europe is Israel's great trade partner, a normative and values source, a source of political and security support, partner to Israel's research funding and the main innovation, as well as partner in culture creation work. The importance of the relationship between Israel and the EU requires Israel to draw attention and resources to its preservation, and even to deepening and expanding it. This article presents principles and recommendations for Israeli policy towards the EU, in four major areas - Israeli conduct in relation to the connection with the EU, political relations, civil relations and economic relations.*

***Key words:** European Union; International economic relations; Economic policy; Political relations.*

PRINCIPII ȘI RECOMANDĂRI PENTRU POLITICA ISRAELULUI FAȚĂ DE UE

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***Adnotare:** Relațiile cu UE sunt un activ strategic și o componentă majoră a statului Israel. Europa este marele partener comercial al Israelului, o sursă normativă și de valori, o sursă de sprijin politic și de securitate, partener pentru finanțarea cercetării Israelului și principala inovație, precum și partener în activitatea de creare a culturii. Importanța relațiilor dintre Israel și UE impune ca Israelul să atragă atenția și resursele pentru menținerea și chiar pentru aprofundarea și extinderea lor. Acest articol prezintă principii și recomandări pentru politica israeliană față de UE, în patru mari domenii -*

comportamentul israelian în raport cu legătura cu UE, relațiile politice, relațiile civile și relațiile economice.

Cuvinte cheie: *Uniunea Europeană; relații economice internaționale; politica economică; relații politice.*

Relationships with the EU are a strategic asset and a major component of the State of Israel. Europe is Israel's great trade partner, a normative and values source, a source of political and security support, partner to Israel's research funding and the main innovation, as well as partner in culture creation work. The importance of the relationship between Israel and the EU requires Israel to draw attention and resources to its preservation, and even to deepening and expanding it.

Israeli Conduct regarding to the relationship with the EU

1. Importance of the relationship between Israel and the EU

Recognizing the asset of relationships with the European Union for Israel. Normatively and values-wise, Israel aspires to belong to the circle of developed democratic and liberal countries, which adhere to the rule of law and protect human rights. In addition, geography also has weight. Despite the accelerated globalization process and the warming of Israel's ties with some Arab countries, Europe is the closest and most significant region to Israel in terms of the depth and diversity of ties with it. Commercially and economically, the European Union is Israel's main trading partner. In 2021, 37% of Israel's goods exports were to the EU (totaling \$16 billion), and in 2020, 34% of services exports (totaling \$12 billion) were to the EU, and 43% of Israel's imports came from the EU. In recent decades, the volume of trade between Israel and the EU has increased significantly.

2. Changing the Israeli Discourse on the Subject of the European Union

Increasing familiarity with the EU and adopting a more positive discourse towards it. In Israel, the EU is often considered a 'punching bag', and by attacking it, as an instrument for mobilizing political and sometimes populist support. This dynamic must be recognized in Israel, reflected in the public discourse, thus contributing to shattering the demonization of the EU. The confrontational Israeli discourse towards the EU, which has gained momentum in recent years, harms the relationship. A positive discourse should be adopted instead, making room for objective mutual criticism. Israeli public figures should increase their acquaintance with Europe and the EU, as a unique entity in the international arena, and understand that this will help them in the political field and in the public arena. They must also speak publicly about the importance of the relationship with

Europe, emphasize to the public the benefits that these relationships generate for both parties and the strategic importance of the relationships and agreements with the EU for Israel's economy, security, innovation and prosperity.

3. Understanding intra-European political conduct and addressing criticism with moderation.

Many countries in the EU prefer that the Union's Foreign Service (European External Service Action) be the one to act as 'bad cop' against Israel, and not themselves. They express their criticism of Israel's policy through the pan-European framework, while in bilateral relations with Israel they generally maintain a positive spirit. However, the foreign policy of the EU is derived directly from decisions made by consensus among the foreign ministers of the member states. It is important that Israel understand this political conduct, and reflect that the EU position represents that of the member states, and not a separate one. Israel needs to deal with the European criticism without exaggerating its reaction to it. There is room for criticism between friends and partners who share the same set of values. Even in times of controversy, Israel should maintain the diplomatic code and a respectful and non-aggressive discourse. There is no need to portray any European criticism as a position that denies the existence of the State of Israel or wishes for its destruction. Not every criticism is anti-Semitism or a call for a boycott.

4. Maintaining a close, continuous and publicly visible political relationship with the European Union

The Prime Minister and the Foreign Minister should pay an official visit to the EU institutions in Brussels. It is important that ministers, Knesset members and senior officials also come to Brussels frequently, as well as to all the member states of the EU. Since EU foreign policy is determined by consensus by all the members, even the smallest countries (such as Luxembourg and Malta) are important - they have a veto right similar to that of the large countries (such as Germany and France), and this increases the need to invest in relationships with them. In addition, a permanent delegation of Knesset members must be established to work with the corresponding delegation in the European Parliament. There are two meetings a year between the delegations, and a permanent core of Knesset members must be created who will participate in these meetings over time.

5. Renewing and upgrading the High-Level Political Dialogue with the European Union

In the past, Israel knew how to derive political benefit from its ties with Europe. This is an important addition to the special relations that Israel has enjoyed over decades with the US and to the ties that it has been developing in recent years with other regions and countries. A central avenue for strengthening the political

relationship with the EU is the official high-level political dialogue within the EU-Israel Association Council. The State of Israel should act to reconvene EU leadership, so as to present its innovative policy. All this in order to create renewed strategic relations with the leadership of the Union and the countries, and upgrade its discourse to a strategic dialogue at the level of cabinet ministers. If this is not possible in light of the opposition of certain European countries, alternative ways must be found to hold a high-level political dialogue between Israel and the EU, for example through launching an informal dialogue channel or visits by the Foreign Minister to Brussels for meetings with the Council of Foreign Ministers of the EU.

In conclusion, Israel must join the European Union in order to promote democratic and liberal values. Despite the location in a 'difficult neighborhood', Israel must continue to strive to belong to the club of democratic-liberal countries, and join hands with the EU to promote this worldview. It must continue to strengthen its membership in the group of European and other western countries in the United Nations, of which Israel has been a member since 2000. Additionally, Israel can join the EU in shared value actions in international institutions and forums, which will promote democracy, human rights and the rule of law, relate positively to the European Union's contribution to civil society in Israel. Israel must recognize the importance of the funding provided by the EU to the activities of democratic and liberal civil society organizations worldwide, including in Israel, and see it as a legitimate and positive investment. Alongside this, efforts should be made to expand the cooperation between civil society organizations in Israel and Europe, and to learn from the EU about the place that non-governmental entities can play in decision-making processes.

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